

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICAL AND HYDRO-PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF IRRIGATED SOILS OF THE LOWER AMUDARYA RIVER

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ABSTRACT

The article provides information on the physical properties of irrigated meadow-alluvial and barren-meadow soils of Chimboy and Shumanay districts: soil bulk density, specific gravity, soil porosity, and water physical properties. The specific gravity is 2.58-2.68 g/cm³ in the upper layers and 2.69-2.75 g/cm³ in the lower layers. Cross-sections were excavated in key areas and it was found that the bulk density of the soil by layer was 1.31-1.38 g/cm³, slightly denser in the lower layers and fluctuated between 1.39-1.45 g/cm³. The specific gravity fluctuated between 2.58-2.68 g/cm³ in the upper layers, while the lower layers were 2.69-2.75 g/cm³. The moisture content of newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils in the studied areas is 1.26-9.22%. In the Kamishariq massif of Chimboy district, the moisture content at wilting is 2.03-7.47%, while in the Bozatou massif this indicator is 1.89-10.69%.

Keywords: general physical properties of meadow-alluvial and takyr-like-meadow soils, specific gravity, bulk density and porosity, maximum hygroscopic moisture content and compaction moisture content.

Introduction: Factors that cause the degradation of agricultural lands in the world are soil erosion, salinization, as well as the depletion of humus and nutrients, pollution with toxic substances and compaction. Since such negative processes constantly occur in the soils of our republic, especially in irrigated soils, they are considered one of the important economic problems of the development of agriculture in our country, and the effective use and protection of land resources by preventing soil degradation and eliminating its consequences has become one of the urgent issues. The fertility of irrigated soils depends on several factors, one of the most important of which is the physical properties of the soil. The physical properties of soils affect the processes of soil formation and the growth and development of plants.

Research object and methods: The object of research is the old and newly irrigated meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils, widespread in the Chimboy and Shumanay districts on the right and left banks of the Lower Amu Darya.

The research was carried out using generally accepted genetic-geographical, profile-geochemical methods for soils [1]. Soil bulk density was determined using a cylinder V-100 cm³, soil specific gravity was determined using a pycnometer; soil porosity was determined by calculation.

The maximum hygroscopicity and wilting moisture of soil layers were determined using the Nikolaev method.

Analysis of literature on the topic: L. Tursunov noted that for irrigated heavy and medium loamy serozem-pasture, meadow, and takyr-like soils formed on loess, alluvial-proluvial, and alluvial deposits common in the serozem and desert regions, the optimal density is 1.2-1.4 g/cm³ and the critical density is 1.5-1.6

g/cm³. In the plowed layer of light loamy soils, the optimal density is 1.34-1.43 g/cm³. [4,5]. Total porosity is closely related to the mechanical composition of the soil and is the largest (50-54%) in sandy, sandy loam and light sandy soils and similar layers. The total porosity of soils is 38-40% in soils with a density of 1.5-1.6 g/cm³, which is considered unsatisfactory. [2,3]. In previously irrigated meadow soils, due to repeated introduction of heavy agricultural machinery into the fields in a state of physical immaturity of the soil and non-compliance with the irrigation regime, soil layers were compacted above the acceptable density (1.55-1.60 g/cm³), and it was found that as the mechanical composition became heavier, the density of the soils also became somewhat higher. In old irrigated meadow soils, the total porosity was 47-51% in the upper layers. In the lower layers, it decreased sharply and was observed in the range of 38-45%, which is considered unsatisfactory. [6]. Various land reclamation measures are used to reduce soil salinity and increase its fertility. These measures are aimed at improving the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil, which ensure good plant growth and development [7, 8]. Scientifically based recommendations have been developed for cleaning the soil from salinity and restoring its fertility. These recommendations include the implementation of land reclamation measures, taking into account the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil [9]. The amount of humus in the soil, the presence of water-soluble salts, the presence of dead water reserves, and the presence of fine particles increase the moisture capacity of the soil, while increasing its density reduces the moisture capacity reserve [10].

Results and their analysis:

The general physical properties of the meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils of the Shumanay (Shumanay and Begjap) and Chimboy (Bozatau and

Qamishariq) districts, which are considered one of the objects of the study, were determined. According to the results obtained, the following analysis can be made. It was found that the specific gravity of the soils of the studied area was in the range of 2.60-2.65 g/cm³ in the upper layers, and fluctuated around 2.67-2.72 g/cm³ in the lower layers as the soil section deepened (pic 1). The reason for the high specific gravity in the lower layers is due to the amount of minerals in the soil. The higher

the level (specific gravity), the more mineralized the soil is. It was found that the optimal value of the bulk density for normal growth of most plants is 1.2-1.3 g/cm³. In these sections, the total porosity was found to be in the range of 46.7-51.1%. It is reported in the literature that the optimal porosity for a number of agricultural crops is about 50%, and if this indicator is less than 40%, it is found that the penetration of their own roots into the soil layers is impeded.

Picture-1 Shumanay massif. Specific and bulk densities of irrigated meadow-alluvial soils, g/cm³

Picture-2. Chimboy district, Kamishariq massif. Specific and bulk densities of irrigated meadow-alluvial soils, g/cm³

According to the results of the analysis of sections 6 and 3 in the meadow-alluvial soils from the Qamisharyk massif to the Olin, the specific gravity in the upper layers fluctuated within 2.58-2.68 g/cm³, while the lower layers were 2.69-2.75 g/cm³. The specific gravity (maximum hygroscopic) depends on the

composition and ratio of mineral and organic substances that make it up. The total porosity was also determined in these sections, which was 45.0-50.7%. (pic 2).

Picture-3. Chimboy district, Bozatau massif. Specific and bulk densities of irrigated takyr-like meadow soils, g/cm³

According to data obtained from the soils of the Bozatau massif, it was determined that the specific gravity of sections 4 and 2 in the takyr-like meadow soils was in the range of 2.62-2.68 g/cm³ in the upper layers and oscillated around 2.70-2.75 g/cm³ in the lower layers. The volume density in these sections was slightly denser in the lower layers than 1.31-1.38 g/cm³ and oscillated in the range of 1.39-1.45 g/cm³. (pic 3).

In order to increase the fertility of the lands of the right and left banks of the Lower Amu Darya, create their optimal land reclamation conditions, irrigation volumes and regimes, it is necessary to conduct a thorough study of the water-physical properties of the lands.

The maximum hygroscopic moisture content (maximum hygroscopic) of soils depends on their mechanical composition, absorption capacity and mineralogical composition, the amount and composition of organic matter, water-soluble salts in them, and the density of soils. As a result of the data obtained during

the research, it was found that the maximum hygroscopic moisture content varies along the soil cross-section. The reason for this is the mechanical composition and chemical properties of soils, the most important of which are the amount of clay and salt. In meadow-alluvial soils distributed on the left bank of the Lower Amu Darya (Shumanay massif, Shumanay district), the content of MG was found to be in the range of 1.68-6.15%. In the Begjap massif, it was found to fluctuate around 1.28-4.60%. In meadow-alluvial soils distributed on the right bank of the Lower Amu Darya, the maximum hygroscopic content was found to fluctuate between 1.36-4.98%, and in barren meadow soils, it fluctuated between 1.26-7.13%.

In the Begjap massif, it was found to fluctuate around 1.28-4.60%. In meadow-alluvial soils distributed on the right bank of the Lower Amu Darya, the maximum hygroscopic content was found to fluctuate between 1.36-4.98%, and in barren meadow soils, it fluctuated between 1.26-7.13%.

Table.

Maximum hygroscopic and storage moisture of meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amu Darya.

Sample №	Cross-sectional depth, cm	MG %	SN %	Sample №	Cross-sectional depth, cm	MG %	SN %
Newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils				Old irrigated meadow-alluvial soils			
Shumanay district Shumanay massif 5	0-43	3,82	5,73	Chimboy district Qamishariq massif 3	0-29	2,71	4,06
	43-65	3,05	4,57		29-48	2,36	3,54
	65-87	1,68	2,52		48-77	1,63	2,45
	87-107	3,98	5,97		77-104	3,46	5,19
	107-131	6,15	9,22		104-127	4,05	6,07
	131-170	5,24	7,86		127-170	2,13	3,19
Newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils				Old irrigated takyr-like-meadow soils			
Shumanay district Shumanay massif 1	0-34	2,08	3,13	Chimboy district Bozatou massif 2	0-28	6,60	9,90
	34-44	1,70	2,55		28-49	5,99	8,98
	44-66	2,13	3,19		49-70	3,57	5,36
	66-84	2,03	3,04		70-93	3,75	5,62
	84-105	2,92	4,38		93-112	3,34	5,01
	105-150	2,69	4,03		112-160	2,35	3,52
Newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils				Old irrigated meadow-alluvial soils			
Shumanay district Shumanay massif 6	0-27	3,13	4,37	Chimboy district Qamishariq massif 6	0-28	3,35	5,02
	27-52	3,35	3,33		28-38	2,57	3,85
	52-76	3,07	2,62		38-59	3,72	5,57
	76-101	3,64	2,44		59-75	3,48	5,23
	101-125	2,03	1,51		75-102	2,17	3,25
	125-160	2,59	1,26		102-160	1,36	2,03
Newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils				Old irrigated meadow-alluvial soils			
Shumanay district Begjap massif 5	0-30	2,95	4,43	Chimboy district Qamishariq massif-5	0-24	3,18	4,77
	30-49	1,47	2,20		24-41	3,72	5,58
	49-108	1,41	2,11		41-62	4,52	6,78
	108-141	1,45	2,18		62-101	4,98	7,47
	141-163	1,89	2,83		101-153	3,02	4,53
Newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils				Old irrigated takyr-like-meadow soils			
Shumanay district Begjap massif 2	0-35	4,60	6,90	Chimboy district Bozatou massif 4	0-24	7,13	10,69
	35-54	1,88	2,81		24-49	4,37	6,55
	54-81	1,28	1,91		49-61	3,33	4,99
	81-115	1,46	2,20		61-75	2,62	3,93
	115-141	1,93	2,89		75-100	2,44	3,66
	141-191	1,43	2,15		100-131	1,51	2,26
				131-200	1,26	1,89	

Studying the wilting moisture content of plants is necessary to determine the lower limit of moisture required by plants, to set the active moisture limits, and to prevent the moisture content in the soil from reaching (wilting moisture). Plants suffer from moisture deficiency when the limit is exceeded, therefore, efforts should be made to avoid lowering the moisture content in the soil from. In the newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils of the studied areas (Shumanay and Begjap massifs of the Shumanay district), the moisture content of the soil is 1.26-9.22%. In the Kamishariq massif of the Chimboy district, the moisture content of the soil is 2.03-7.47%, and in the Bozatou massif this indicator is 1.89-10.69%. The high moisture content of the soil in the barren meadow soils is explained as follows. Such soils have a large number of clay par-

ticles, retain more moisture, and have low plant uptake, which is mainly characteristic of saline soils. According to the data on the relationship between plant wilting moisture and soil density, soil density makes it difficult for plants to absorb moisture. The change in wilting moisture indicators in the upper layers is due to the uneven mechanical composition, density, and salt content (table).

Conclusion: The general physical properties of meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amu Darya were determined, and the general porosity was observed to be satisfactory and unsatisfactory in the sections where it was determined. The bulk density was found to be medium in the arable layers and strongly concentrated in the sub-arable layers. According to the relative density, it was found to be medium and high in

the arable and sub-arable layers. In old irrigated meadow-alluvial soils, the soil porosity was found to be somewhat lower than in the newly irrigated areas. As a comment, we can say that this, in turn, is explained by the state of soil culture, the duration of the irrigation period, and the agro-ameliorative conditions used. It has been observed that the general physical properties of irrigated soils on the right and left banks of the Lower Amu Darya have changed under the influence of degradation processes, which affects soil fertility and agronomic properties.

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